

1 **Life cycle-associated regulation of the ERBB gene family by IKZF transcription factors.**

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7 We studied genomic structure associated with and proximal to the ERBB gene family, including EGFR
8 (HER1), ERBB2 (HER2), ERBB3 and ERBB4. We found that each ERBB gene, encoded on separate
9 chromosomes, was located proximal to a separate IKZF transcription factor. The genomic structure of the
10 ERBB-IKZF encoding regions, including genes encoding Igfbp gene members, suggested a function
11 related to growth factor regulation. ATAC-seq occupancy studies of cells expressing CRISPR-engineered
12 IKZF1 deletions revealed direct occupancy of EGFR (HER1) by IKZF1. On chromosome 7, IKZF1 was
13 located proximal to both EGFR and IGFBP3; direct regulation of IGFBP3 by IKZF1 was also observed. In
14 humans with breast cancer, where ERBB2 is a subtype-determining factor, IKZF1 was activated during
15 progression from primary tumor to lymph node metastasis then coordinately silenced from lymph node
16 metastasis to CNS metastasis. The studies reveal unprecedented features of the human genomic
17 structure with functional impact on the tumor life cycle.
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